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* Corresponding author.

dranibansal@gmail.com

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Common Fixed Point Results for Generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -Weak Contraction Maps and their Applications to Best Approximation

Reetu¹, Dinesh Rani Bansal^{2*}¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Vaish College, Rohtak, 124001² Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, Vaish College, Rohtak, 124001

Abstract

Objective/Aim: To find the fixed point theorems and best approximation results for the pair of self maps in the setting of metric and normed spaces.

Methods: We used the notion of generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction for pair of maps in metric spaces and property (N) in Normed spaces.

Findings: Unique common fixed points for four maps satisfying generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction condition and some best approximation results have been established. **Novelty/Improvements:** Our results extend and improve the existing results of Dahiya et al., Arya et al., He and Zhao etc. Examples have also been added in support of our results.

Keywords: Metric space; Normed space; Common fixed point; Generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction; Best approximation

1 Introduction

In 1997, Alber and Guerre-Delabriere⁽¹⁾ generalized the Banach contraction principle by introducing the concept of weakly contractive mappings and proving the existence of fixed points for weakly contractive mappings in Hilbert spaces. Thereafter, Rhoades⁽²⁾ assumed ϕ -weakly contractive mappings and Zhang and Song⁽³⁾ introduced the generalized ϕ -weak contraction and proved the fixed point results for these mappings. Further, using the control function defined by Khan et al.⁽⁴⁾, the above results have been generalized by many authors.

On the other hand, Berinde⁽⁵⁾ introduced the notion of (k, L) -weak contraction and proved that many well known contractive conditions do imply (k, L) -weak contraction. Afterward, many authors studied this new class of weak contractions and obtained some significant results. In 2014, Rathee et al.⁽⁶⁾ introduced the notion of $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction and proved a fixed point result for this contraction. In 2017, He et al.⁽⁷⁾ proved the common fixed point theorem for two mappings satisfying a generalized (φ, ϕ) -weak contractive type condition in a complete metric space. Afterwards, Dahiya et al.⁽⁸⁾ established common fixed point results for generalized (φ, ϕ) -weak contractive

mappings with constants in complete metric spaces. In 2023, Arya et al⁽⁹⁾ generalized the results of He et al.⁽⁷⁾.

In the present paper, we introduce the notion of generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction for the pair of self mappings and obtain common fixed point results for $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, which generalize the existing results for generalized (φ, ϕ) -weak contractive type conditions. As an application, some best approximation results are also established which generalize and extend various known results existing in literature.

Preliminaries

We now give some known definitions and standard notations that will be needed in the sequel:

Definition 2.1: Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a normed space and $T, S: X \rightarrow X$. A point $x \in X$ is called:

- (1) fixed point of T if $Tx = x$.
- (2) coincidence point of the pair $\{S, T\}$ if $Tx = Sx$,
- (3) common fixed point of the pair $\{S, T\}$ if $x = Tx = Sx$.

We shall denote by $\text{Fix}(T)$ the set of all fixed points of T and by $C(S, T)$ the set of all coincidence points of S and T .

Definition 2.2: Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a normed space and $T, S: X \rightarrow X$. The pair $\{S, T\}$ is called weakly compatible if $STx = TSx$ for all $x \in C(S, T)$.

Definition 2.3: A subset M of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is said to be convex if the segment $[x, y] = \{(1 - k)x + ky : 0 \leq k \leq 1\}$, joining x to y is contained in M for all $x, y \in M$ and $k \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.4: The subset M of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is said to be q -starshaped if there exists $q \in M$ such that the segment $[q, x] = \{(1 - k)q + kx : 0 \leq k \leq 1\}$, joining q to x is contained in M for all $x \in M$ and $k \in [0, 1]$.

Remark 2.5: Clearly, q -starshaped subsets of X contain all convex subsets of X as a proper subclass.

Definition 2.6⁽¹⁰⁾: A subset M of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is said to have property (N) with respect to T if

- (i) $T: M \rightarrow M$,
- (ii) $(1 - k_n)q + k_nTx \in M$, for some $q \in M$ and a fixed sequence of real numbers k_n ($0 < k_n < 1$) converging to 1 and for each $x \in M$.

Remark 2.7⁽¹⁰⁾: It is to be noted that each T -invariant q -starshaped set has property (N) but converse does not hold in general. This is shown by the following example:

Example 2.8⁽¹⁰⁾: Let $X = \mathbb{R}$ be the set of real numbers and $M = \{\frac{1}{n}\}$, where n is a natural number} be endowed with the usual norm. Define $Tx = 1$ for each $x \in M$.

Then clearly, M is not

q -starshaped, but has property (N) with respect to T , for $q = 1, k_n = 1 - \frac{1}{n}$.

Definition 2.9: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ and $x \in X$. If there exists an element y_0 in M such that $d(x, y_0) = d(x, M)$, then y_0 is called best approximations to x out of M . We denote by $P_M(x)$, the set of all best approximation to x out of M .

2 Main Results

First, we introduce the concept of generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction for the pair of self mappings in the following way:

Definition 3.1: Let $S, T: X \rightarrow X$ be two self maps on the metric space (X, d) . Then the pair $\{S, T\}$ is called a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction if for each $x, y \in X$

$$\varphi(d(Sx, Ty)) \leq \varphi(m(x, y)) - \phi(m(x, y)) + L\varphi(n(x, y)),$$

where $f, g: X \rightarrow X, L \geq 0$,

$$m(x, y) = \max\{d(fx, gy), d(fx, Sx), d(gy, Ty), \frac{1}{2}[d(fx, Ty) + d(gy, Sx)]\},$$

$$n(x, y) = \min\{[d(fx, Sx) + d(gy, Ty)], d(gy, Sx), d(fx, Ty)\},$$

and $\varphi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous nondecreasing function with $\varphi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$ and $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a lower semi continuous function from right such that ϕ is positive on $(0, \infty)$ and $\phi(0) = 0$.

Remark 3.2: (i) If we take $S = T$ in the above definition, then T is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction.

(ii) if $f = g = I$ (identity map), then $\{S, T\}$ is called generalized (φ, ϕ, L) -weak contraction and if $S = T$, then T is called a generalized (φ, ϕ, L) -weak contraction.

(iii) If $L = 0$ and $g = f =$ identity map, that is, $m(x, y)$ coincides with $M(x, y)$, then $\{S, T\}$ is called generalized (φ, ϕ) -weak contraction.

(iv) If $S = T, L = 0$ and $\varphi(t) = t$, then T is called a generalized

$\varphi_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, which is the same as the generalized (f, g) -weak contraction investigated by Akbar et al. (see⁽¹¹⁾) and if $\varphi(t) = (1 - k)t$ for a constant k with $0 < k < 1$, then T is called generalized (f, g) -contraction.

We now prove our main result which extends and improves many existing results, including the results of Rathee et al⁽⁶⁾ and Dahiya et al.⁽⁸⁾. The following lemma is needed to prove our main result:

Lemma 3.3 ⁽⁶⁾: If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(y_{n+1}, y_n) = 0$ and $\{y_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence and converges to z , then $\{y_{2n+1}\}$ also converges to z .

Theorem 3.4: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and f, g, S, T be self mappings of M such that $cl(T(M)) \subseteq f(M)$ and $cl(S(M)) \subseteq g(M)$. Assume that $cl(T(M))$ or $cl(S(M))$ is complete and the pair $\{S, T\}$ is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction. If the pairs $\{f, S\}$ and $\{g, T\}$ are weakly compatible, then $M \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T)$ is singleton, i.e., f, g, S, T have a unique common fixed point in M .

Proof: Let x_0 be an arbitrary point in M . Since $cl(T(M)) \subseteq f(M)$, we can find $x_1 \in M$ such that $Tx_0 = fx_1$, and also, as $cl(S(M)) \subseteq g(M)$, there exists $x_2 \in M$ such that $Sx_1 = gx_2$. Continuing this process, we obtain a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in M such that for every $n \geq 0$,

$$y_{2n} = Tx_{2n-1} \text{ and } y_{2n+1} = Sx_{2n} = gx_{2n+1}.$$

If, for some n , $y_{2n} = y_{2n+1}$, then $\{y_n\}$ turns out to be a constant sequence, hence it is Cauchy. Now suppose that $y_{2n} \neq y_{2n+1}$.

Using the fact that $\{S, T\}$ is generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, for each $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\varphi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) = \varphi(d(Sx_{2n}, Tx_{2n})) \leq \varphi(m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})) - \phi(m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})) + L\varphi(n(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})) \tag{3.1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}) &= \max \{d(fx_{2n+1}, gx_{2n}), d(fx_{2n+1}, Sx_{2n+1}), d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n}), \\ &\quad \frac{1}{2} [d(fx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n}) + d(gx_{2n}, Sx_{2n+1})]\} \\ &= \max \{d(y_{2n}, y_{2n-1}), d(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}), d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}), \frac{1}{2} [d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1})]\} \\ &\leq \max \{d(y_{2n}, y_{2n-1}), d(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}), \frac{1}{2} [d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + d(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1})]\} \\ n(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}) &= \min \{[d(fx_{2n+1}, Sx_{2n+1}) + (gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n})], d(gx_{2n}, Sx_{2n+1}), d(fx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n})\} \\ &= \min \{[d(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) + d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n})], d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}), 0\} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\varphi(0) = 0$, and $n(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}) = 0$, therefore eqn. (3.1) becomes

$$\varphi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) \leq \varphi(m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})) - \phi(m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})) \tag{3.2}$$

This implies that

$$\varphi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) \leq \varphi(m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n})).$$

As φ is a nondecreasing function, therefore, for each $n \geq 0$, we have

$$d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \leq m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}).$$

Now, we show that $\{d(y_{n+1}, y_n)\}$ is monotonically decreasing sequence.

If possible, let $d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) > d(y_{2n}, y_{2n-1})$, then, by (3.1),

$$m(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}) \leq d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \text{ which implies that}$$

$$\varphi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) \leq \varphi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) - \phi(d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) \tag{3.3}$$

This is a contradiction since $\phi(t) > 0$. Therefore, we have

$$d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \leq d(y_{2n}, y_{2n-1}).$$

Similarly, it can be shown that $d(y_{2n}, y_{2n-1}) \leq d(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n-2})$. Therefore, for each $n \geq 0$, we have $d(y_{n+1}, y_n) \leq d(y_n, y_{n-1})$.

Thus, the sequence $\{d(y_{n+1}, y_n)\}$ is nonincreasing. Also, the sequence $\{d(y_{n+1}, y_n)\}$ is bounded below, therefore, there exists $r \geq 0$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(y_{n+1}, y_n) = r.$$

After letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.3), we obtain $\varphi(r) \leq \varphi(r) - \phi(r)$, which is a contradiction unless $r = 0$. Hence,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(y_{n+1}, y_n) = 0 \tag{3.4}$$

Now, we show that $\{y_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in M . Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $m > n$. Then,

$$d(y_{2n}, y_{2m}) \leq d(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) + d(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+2}) + \dots + d(y_{2m-1}, y_{2m})$$

Now, taking the limit as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$ and using (3.4), we get

$$\lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} d(y_{2n}, y_{2m}) = 0. \text{ Thus, } \{y_{2n}\} \text{ is a Cauchy sequence in } cl(T(M)). \text{ Therefore, by the completeness of } cl(T(M)), \text{ there exists}$$

some $z \in cl(T(M))$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{2n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_{2n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} fx_{2n+1} = z \tag{3.5}$$

By Lemma 3.3, $\{y_{2n+1}\}$ also converges to z . Therefore,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{2n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_{2n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} gx_{2n+2} = z \tag{3.6}$$

Further, $cl(T(M)) \subseteq f(M)$, therefore there exists $u \in M$ such that $fu = z$. Now, we show that u is a coincidence point of S and f in M . Since $\{S, T\}$ is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, therefore, we have

$$\leq \varphi(m(u, x_{2n})) - \phi(m(u, x_{2n})) + L\varphi(n(u, x_{2n})), \tag{3.7}$$

where

$$m(u, x_{2n}) = \max \{d(fu, gx_{2n}), d(fu, Su), d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n}), \frac{1}{2} [d(fu, Tx_{2n}) + d(gx_{2n}, Su)]\}$$

$$n(u, x_{2n}) = \min \{[d(fu, Su) + d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n})], d(gx_{2n}, Su), d(fu, Tx_{2n})\}$$

Now using (3.5) and (3.6), we get $m(u, x_{2n}) \rightarrow d(Su, z)$ and $n(u, x_{2n}) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.7), we get

$$\varphi(d(Su, z)) \leq \varphi(d(Su, z)) - \phi(d(Su, z)).$$

This is true only if $d(Su, z) = 0$, that is, $Su = z$. But $z = fu$, therefore, $Su = fu$. Thus, u is coincidence point of S and f in M .

Since the pair $\{f, S\}$ is weakly compatible, therefore,

$Sz = Sf u = fSu = fz$. Now, we show that $Sz = z$. Since $\{S, T\}$ is generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, we have

$$\varphi(d(Sz, fx_{2n+1})) = \varphi(d(Sz, Tx_{2n}))$$

$$\leq \varphi(m(z, x_{2n})) - \phi(m(z, x_{2n})) + L\varphi(n(z, x_{2n})) \tag{3.8}$$

where

$$m(z, x_{2n}) = \max \{d(fz, gx_{2n}), d(fz, Sz), d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n}), \frac{1}{2} [d(fz, Tx_{2n}) + d(gx_{2n}, Sz)]\}$$

$$= \max \{d(Sz, gx_{2n}), d(Sz, Sz), d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n}), \frac{1}{2} [d(Sz, Tx_{2n}) + d(gx_{2n}, Sz)]\}$$

$$n(z, x_{2n}) = \min \{[d(fz, Sz) + d(gx_{2n}, Tx_{2n})], d(gx_{2n}, Sz), d(fz, Tx_{2n})\}$$

Now using (3.5) and (3.6), we can write

$$m(z, x_{2n}) \rightarrow d(Sz, z) \text{ and } n(z, x_{2n}) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Therefore, letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.8), we get

$$\varphi(d(Sz, z)) \leq \varphi(d(Sz, z)) - \phi(d(Sz, z)).$$

This is true only if $d(Sz, z) = 0$; that is, $Sz = z = fz$.

The next step is to show that z is also a common fixed point for mappings g and T . Since $cl(S(M)) \subseteq g(M)$, there exists a point y in M such that $Sz = gy$. Now, we show that $gy = Ty$,

$$\varphi(d(gy, Ty)) = \varphi(d(Sz, Ty))$$

$$\leq \varphi(m(z, y)) - \phi(m(z, y)) + L\varphi(n(z, y)),$$

where

$$m(z, y) = \max \{d(fz, gy), d(fz, Sz), d(gy, Ty), \frac{1}{2} [d(fz, Ty) + d(gy, Sz)]\}$$

$$= \max \{0, 0, d(gy, Ty), \frac{1}{2} [d(gy, Ty) + 0]\} = d(gy, Ty)$$

$$n(z, y) = \min \{[d(fz, Sz) + d(gy, Ty)], d(gy, Sz), d(fz, Ty)\} = 0.$$

Thus, we get

$$\varphi(d(gy, Ty)) \leq \varphi(d(gy, Ty)) - \phi(d(gy, Ty)).$$

This is true only if $d(gy, Ty) = 0$; that is, $gy = Ty$. Now since $\{g, T\}$ is weakly compatible, therefore $Tz = TSz = Tgy = gTy = gz$.

Finally, we show that $Tz = z$.

$$\varphi(d(z, Tz)) = \varphi(d(Sz, Tz))$$

$$\leq \varphi(m(z, z)) - \phi(m(z, z)) + L\varphi(n(z, z)),$$

where

$$m(z, z) = \max \{d(fz, gz), d(fz, Sz), d(gz, Tz), \frac{1}{2} [d(fz, Tz) + d(gz, Sz)]\}$$

$$= \max \{d(z, Tz), 0, 0, \frac{1}{2} [d(z, Tz) + d(z, Tz)]\} = d(z, Tz)$$

$$n(z, z) = \min \{[d(fz, Sz) + d(gz, Ty)], d(gz, Sz), d(fz, Ty)\} = 0.$$

Thus, we get

$$\varphi(d(z, Tz)) \leq \varphi(d(z, Tz)) - \phi(d(z, Tz)),$$

which implies $z = Tz$ and hence $Sz = fz = Tz = gz = z$. Thus, z is common fixed point of f, g, S and T in M .

The proof is similar if $cl(S(M))$ is complete. Moreover, it can be easily shown that this z is unique and hence, $M \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T)$ is singleton.

Now, we give an example in support of Theorem 3.4:

Example 3.5: Let $X = R$ and $M = [0, 1)$ be equipped with the usual metric $d(x, y) = |x - y|$ for $x, y \in X$. Let $f, g, S, T: M \rightarrow M$ be defined by

$$S(x) = \log(1 + x), T(x) = \log(1 + \frac{x}{4}), f(x) = e^{4x} - 1 \text{ and } g(x) = e^x - 1.$$

Define $\varphi, \phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by $\varphi(t) = 2t$ and $\phi(t) = \frac{3}{2}t$ for all $t \geq 0$.

Now we will show that $\{S, T\}$ is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction. Let $x, y \in M$, then using the mean value theorem, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(d(Sx, Ty)) &= 2 d(Sx, Ty) = 2 |Sx - Ty| = 2 \left| \log(1 + x) - \log(1 + \frac{y}{4}) \right| \leq 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} |4x - y| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} |e^{4x} - e^y| \\ &= \frac{1}{2} |fx - gy| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ |fx - gy|, |fx - Sx|, |gy - Ty|, \frac{1}{2} [|fx - Ty| + |gy - Sx|] \right\}, \\ &= \frac{1}{2} m(x, y) = 2 m(x, y) - \frac{3}{2} m(x, y) \\ &= \varphi(m(x, y)) - \phi(m(x, y)). \end{aligned}$$

This yields that

$$\varphi(d(Sx, Ty)) \leq \varphi(m(x, y)) - \phi(m(x, y)) + L \varphi(n(x, y)),$$

holds for all $L \geq 0$. Therefore, all the conditions of Theorem 3.4 are satisfied and hence S, T, f, g have a common fixed point.

Here it is clear that 0 is the unique common fixed point of S, T, f and g .

Remark 3.6: If we take $S = T$ in Theorem 3.4, then we have the following result of Rathee et al.:

Corollary 3.7 ⁽⁶⁾: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and f, g and T be self-mappings of M such that $cl(T(M)) \subseteq f(M) \cap g(M)$. Assume that $cl(T(M))$ is complete and T is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction. Then the pair (T, f) and (T, g) have a unique point of coincidence in M . Also, if the pairs (T, f) and (T, g) are weakly compatible, then $M \cap Fix(f) \cap Fix(g) \cap Fix(T)$ is singleton.

Corollary 3.8: Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and let T be a self-mapping of X . If T is a generalized (φ, ϕ) -weak contraction, then T has a unique fixed point.

Remark 3.9: If we take $f = g =$ identity mappings in Theorem 3.4, then we have the following result:

Corollary 3.10: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and let S and T be self-mappings of M such that $cl(T(M)) \subseteq M$ and $cl(S(M)) \subseteq M$. Assume that $cl(T(M))$ or $cl(S(M))$ is complete and the pair $\{S, T\}$ is generalized (φ, ϕ, L) -weak contraction. Then, $M \cap Fix(S) \cap Fix(T)$ is singleton.

Now, we prove another fixed point result using corollary 3.10:

Theorem 3.11: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and f, g, S, T be self mappings of M such that $cl(T(M))$ or $cl(S(M))$ is complete and the pair $\{S, T\}$ is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction. Further assume that $Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is nonempty, $cl(S(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ and $cl(T(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$. Then $M \cap Fix(S) \cap Fix(T) \cap Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is singleton.

Proof: Firstly, suppose that $cl(T(M))$ is complete. Then $cl(T(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)))$ is complete by the completeness of $cl(T(M))$.

Now, for any $x, y \in Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(d(Sx, Ty)) &\leq \varphi(m(x, y)) - \phi(m(x, y)) + L\varphi(n(x, y)), \\ &= \varphi(M(x, y)) - \phi(M(x, y)) + L\varphi(N(x, y)), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$M(x, y) = \max\{d(x, y), d(x, Sx), d(y, Ty), \frac{1}{2} [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Sx)]\},$$

$$N(x, y) = \min \{[d(x, Sx) + d(y, Ty)], d(y, Sx), d(x, Ty)\}.$$

Hence $\{S, T\}$ is generalized (φ, ϕ, L) -weak contraction mapping on $Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$. Also, $cl(S(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ and $cl(T(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$, therefore by corollary 3.10, S and T have a common fixed point in $Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ and consequently, $M \cap Fix(S) \cap Fix(T) \cap Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is singleton.

The proof is similar if $cl(S(M))$ is complete.

Corollary 3.12 ⁽⁶⁾: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and f, g and T be self-mappings of M such that $cl(T(M))$ is complete, T is generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, $Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is nonempty and $cl(T(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$. Then, $M \cap Fix(T) \cap Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is singleton.

In Theorem 3.11, if we take $S = T$ and $L = 0$, then we easily obtain the following results which properly contains Theorem 3.3 of Akbar et al. ⁽¹¹⁾.

Corollary 3.13: Let M be a nonempty subset of a metric space (X, d) and f, g, T be self mappings of M such that $cl(T(M))$ is complete, T is a generalized $(\varphi, \phi)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction, $Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is nonempty and $cl(T(Fix(f) \cap Fix(g))) \subseteq Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$. Then $M \cap Fix(T) \cap Fix(f) \cap Fix(g)$ is singleton.

Common Fixed Point Theorems for Generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -Weak Contraction in Normed Spaces:

Now, we prove common fixed point results for generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction in the setting of normed spaces, which contain similar results of Akbar et al. (11) and Rathee et al. (6):

Theorem 4.1: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space X and S, T, f and g be self-maps of M . If $\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to S and T , $\text{cl}(T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $\text{cl}(S(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and S, T, f, g satisfy

$$\varphi(k\|Sx - Ty\|) \leq \varphi(m_1(x, y)) - k\phi(m_1(x, y)) + kL\varphi(n_1(x, y)) \tag{4.1}$$

for all $k \in (0, 1)$ and $x, y \in M$, where

- (a) $\varphi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous monotone nondecreasing function with $\varphi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$,
- (b) $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a lower semicontinuous function from right such that $\phi(t) > 0$ if $t > 0$ and $\phi(0) = 0$,
- (c) $m_1(x, y) = \max\{\|fx - gy\|, \text{dist}(fx, [q, Sx]), \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty]), \frac{1}{2}[\text{dist}(gy, [q, Sx]) + \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])]\}$,
- (d) $n_1(x, y) = \min\{[\text{dist}(fx, [q, Sx]) + \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty])], \text{dist}(gy, [q, Sx]), \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])\}$

Then, $M \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$, provided that $\text{cl}(S(M))$ or $\text{cl}(T(M))$ is compact, S and T are continuous.

Proof: As $T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$, $S(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to S and T , therefore, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we can define $T_n: \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \rightarrow \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ by $T_n x = (1 - k_n)q + k_n T x$ and $S_n x = (1 - k_n)q + k_n S x$, for all $x \in \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and a fixed sequence of real numbers k_n ($0 < k_n < 1$) converging to 1. Since $\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to S, T and $\text{cl}(T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$, $\text{cl}(S(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$, we have $\text{cl}(T_n(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $\text{cl}(S_n(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Also, by the inequality (4.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\|S_n x - T_n y\|) &= \varphi(k_n \|Sx - Ty\|) \\ &\leq \varphi(m_1(x, y)) - k_n \phi(m_1(x, y)) + k_n L \varphi(n_1(x, y)) \\ &= \varphi(m_1(x, y)) - \phi_n(m_1(x, y)) + L_n \varphi(n_1(x, y)), \end{aligned}$$

where $\phi_n = k_n \phi, L_n = k_n L$,

$$\begin{aligned} m_1(x, y) &= \max\{\|fx - gy\|, \text{dist}(fx, [q, Sx]), \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty]), \frac{1}{2}[\text{dist}(gy, [q, Sx]) \\ &+ \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])]\}, \\ &\leq \max\{\|fx - gy\|, \|fx - S_n x\|, \|gy - T_n y\|, \frac{1}{2}[\|gy - S_n x\| + \|fx - T_n y\|]\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} n_1(x, y) &= \min\{[\text{dist}(fx, [q, Sx]) + \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty])], \text{dist}(gy, [q, Sx]), \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])\}, \\ &\leq \min\{[\|fx - S_n x\| + \|gy - T_n y\|], \|gy - S_n x\|, \|fx - T_n y\|\}. \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $0 < k_n < 1$. Clearly, $\phi_n: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a lower semicontinuous function from right such that ϕ_n is positive on $(0, \infty)$ and $\phi_n(0) = 0$ and $L_n \geq 0$. Thus, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\{S_n, T_n\}$ is generalized $(\varphi, \phi_n, L_n)_{f, g}$ -weak contraction.

Now, suppose that $\text{cl}(T(M))$ is compact. Therefore, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\text{cl}(T_n(M))$ is compact and hence complete for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. By Theorem 3.11, for each $n \geq 1$, there exists $\{x_n\}$ in M such that $x_n = f(x_n) = g(x_n) = S_n(x_n) = T_n(x_n)$.

Again, the compactness of $\text{cl}(T(M))$ implies that there exists a subsequence $\{Tx_m\}$ of $\{Tx_n\}$ such that $Tx_m \rightarrow z \in \text{cl}(T(M))$. Since $\{Tx_m\}$ is a sequence in $T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))$ and $\text{cl}(T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$, therefore $z \in \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$.

Moreover

$$x_m = T_m(x_m) = (1 - k_m)q + k_m T x_m \rightarrow z,$$

As S and T are continuous on M , we have $Sz = Tz = z$. Similarly, we can prove the result if $\text{cl}(S(M))$ is compact. Thus, $M \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

In theorem 4.1, if we take $S = T$, then we obtain the following result, which generalize the result of Rathee et al. (6):

Corollary 4.2 : Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space X and T, f, g be self-maps of M . If $\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to T , $\text{cl}(T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and T, f, g satisfy

$$\varphi(k\|Tx - Ty\|) \leq \varphi(m_1(x, y)) - k\phi(m_1(x, y)) + kL\varphi(n_1(x, y)),$$

for all $k \in (0, 1)$ and $x, y \in M$, where

- (a) $\varphi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous monotone nondecreasing function with $\varphi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$,
- (b) $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a lower semicontinuous function from right such that ϕ is positive on $(0, \infty)$ and $\phi(0) = 0$,
- (c) $m_1(x, y) = \max\{\|fx - gy\|, \text{dist}(fx, [q, Tx]), \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty]), \frac{1}{2}[\text{dist}(gy, [q, Tx]) + \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])]\}$,
- (d) $n_1(x, y) = \min\{[\text{dist}(fx, [q, Tx]) + \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty])], \text{dist}(gy, [q, Tx]), \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])\}$

Then, $M \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$, provided that $\text{cl}(T(M))$ is compact and T is continuous.

In Theorem 4.1, if we take $S = T$, $\varphi(t) = t$ and $\phi(t) = (\frac{1}{k} - 1)t$ for a constant k with $0 < k < 1$, then we easily obtain the following result:

Corollary 4.3: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space X and T, f and g be self-maps of M . If $\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to T , $\text{cl}(T(\text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g))) \subseteq \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and T, f, g satisfy

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq m_1(x, y) + Ln_1(x, y), \text{ for all } x, y \in M, \text{ where}$$

$$m_1(x, y) = \max\{\|fx - gy\|, \text{dist}(fx, [q, Tx]), \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty]), \frac{1}{2}[\text{dist}(gy, [q, Tx]) + \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])]\},$$

$$n_1(x, y) = \min\{[\text{dist}(fx, [q, Tx]) + \text{dist}(gy, [q, Ty])], \text{dist}(gy, [q, Tx]), \text{dist}(fx, [q, Ty])\}$$

Then, $M \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$, provided that $\text{cl}(T(M))$ is compact and T is continuous.

Applications to Best Approximation:

Theorem 5.1: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space X and S, T, f, g be self mappings of X . If $u \in X$ and $D = P_M(u)$, $D_0 = D \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ is q -starshaped, $\text{cl}(S(D_0)) \subseteq D_0$ and $\text{cl}(T(D_0)) \subseteq D_0$, $\text{cl}(S(D))$ or $\text{cl}(T(D))$ is compact, S and T are continuous on D and (4.1) holds for all $x, y \in D$. Then, $P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: Since D_0 is q -starshaped set and it is S and T -invariant, therefore, D_0 satisfies property (N) with respect to S and T . Also, all the conditions of theorem 4.1 are satisfied; therefore by theorem 4.1, $P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

We now give another best approximation result:

Theorem 5.2: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ and S, T, f and g be continuous self mappings of X such that $S(\partial M \cap M) \subseteq M$ and $T(\partial M \cap M) \subseteq M$, where ∂M denotes the boundary of M . Let u be common fixed point of f, g, S, T for some $u \in X \setminus M$. Further suppose that $D = P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to S and T and $q \in \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $f(D) = g(D) = D$. If the conditions $\|Sx - Tu\| \leq \|fx - gu\|$ and $\|Su - Ty\| \leq \|fu - gy\|$ and (4.1) holds for all $x, y \in D$ and one of the $\text{cl}(S(D))$ or $\text{cl}(T(D))$ is compact, then $P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Let $x \in D$. Then, for any $h \in (0, 1)$, $\|hu + (1-h)x - u\| = (1-h)\|x - u\| < \text{dist}(u, M)$. It follows that the line segment $\{hu + (1-h)x : 0 < h < 1\}$ and the set M are disjoint. Thus x is not in the interior of M and so $x \in \partial M \cap M$. Since $S(\partial M \cap M) \subseteq M$ and $T(\partial M \cap M) \subseteq M$, therefore, Sx and Tx must be in M . Also, since $f(D) = D$, $fx \in D$ and u is common fixed point of f, g, S, T , therefore, from the given contractive condition, we obtain

$$\|Sx - u\| = \|Sx - Tu\| \leq \|fx - gu\| = \|fx - u\| = d(u, M),$$

and $\|u - Tx\| = \|Su - Tx\| \leq \|fu - gx\| = \|u - gx\| = d(u, M)$. Thus, D is both S and T -invariant. Hence, $S(D) \subset D = g(D)$ and $T(D) \subset D = f(D)$. Thus all the conditions of the theorem 4.1 are satisfied; therefore, there exists $z \in D$ such that z is a common fixed point of S and T , i.e., $P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

Corollary 5.3: Let M be a nonempty subset of a normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ and T, f and g be continuous self mappings of X such that $T(\partial M \cap M) \subseteq M$, where ∂M denotes boundary of M . Let u be common fixed point of f, g and T for some $u \in X \setminus M$. Further suppose that $D = P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ has the property (N) with respect to T and $q \in \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g)$ and $f(D) = g(D) = D$. If the conditions $\|Tx - Tu\| \leq \|fx - gu\|$ and (4.1) holds for all $x, y \in D$ and $\text{cl}(T(D))$ is compact, then $P_M(u) \cap \text{Fix}(S) \cap \text{Fix}(T) \cap \text{Fix}(f) \cap \text{Fix}(g) \neq \emptyset$.

Remark 5.4: Corollary 5.1 and Theorem 5.2 extend and generalize the corresponding results of Akbar et al.⁽¹¹⁾ and Rathee et al.⁽⁶⁾.

3 Conclusion

In this paper, we extend the notion of generalized $(\varphi, \phi, L)_{f,g}$ -weak contraction mappings to the pair of mappings and prove the common fixed point theorems for such types of mappings in the setting of metric space and normed space. As an application, some best approximation results have also been established. The results proved in this paper generalize various known existing results in the literature. Examples are also given that verify our theorems.

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